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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF Q-ABSORBANCE RATIO UV-SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF METFORMIN AND CANAGLIFLOZIN IN BULK AND COMBINED DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A rapid, simple, accurate and precise UV spectrophotometric Q-absorption ratio method was developed and validated as per the ICH-Q2 guidelines for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin. The method involved Q-absorption ratio analysis using two wavelengths obtained by the overlay spectrum of the Metformin and Canagliflozin, with one being the maximum absorbance wavelength of Canagliflozin (220 nm, λ_2) and the other being the iso-absorptive point of both drugs (250 nm, λ_1). The method was validated as per ICH guidelines. Linearity and range were determined by analyzing six independent concentration levels of calibration curve in the range of 5-17.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively ($n=3$). The value of correlation coefficient was > 0.99 for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin at 220nm and 250 nm. Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from marketed formulation at three levels – 80,100 and 120% of standard addition; the accuracy ranged between 99.63 and 101.14%. Intra-day and inter-day precision of Metformin and Canagliflozin was determined for three concentrations 5, 10 and 17.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 220 nm, 240 nm and 250 nm; and % CV was $<1.0\%$. The proposed UV spectrophotometric Q-absorption ratio method is rapid, simple, precise, reproducible and economical that can be successfully employed for the industrial analysis of the combination of Metformin and Canagliflozin.

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INTRODUCTION

Type 2 Diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the most prevalent metabolic disease worldwide. Inadequate management and control of hyperglycemia in patients with T2DM lead to long-term complications due to the chronic and progressive nature of the disease arising from pathophysiology of beta-cell dysfunction, insulin resistance and increased hepatic glucose output. Patients with T2DM often require a combination of therapeutic agents to achieve glycemic control over the long term [1-6]. The American Diabetes Association and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes have recently recommended that patients who are inadequately controlled on Metformin use additional anti-hyperglycemic agents that have complimentary mechanisms of action [3].

Metformin is the most commonly prescribed oral antidiabetic agent. It is recommended as a first-line therapy in the management of T2DM when hyperglycemia is not satisfactorily managed by diet alone. Metformin decreases hepatic glucose production and intestinal absorption of glucose, and improves insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization [7,8]. Metformin is chemically 1- carbamiimidamido-N, N-dimethylmethaniimidamide (Figure-1a). Metformin immediate release (IR) tablets are available at 500, 850, and 1,000 mg strengths of metformin hydrochloride (HCl) and are administered 2 or 3 times daily up to a maximum recommended a daily dose of 2,550 mg in adults [9,10].

Canagliflozin (Invokana®; Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Inc.) belongs to a novel class of orally active inhibitors of renal sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2). It decreases the extent of glucose reabsorption from the proximal tubules of the kidney, thereby increasing urinary glucose excretion (UGE) and decreasing plasma glucose levels in patients with hyperglycemia [11-21]. Canagliflozin is chemically (2S, 3R, 4R, 5S, 6R)-2-(3-{[5-(4-fluorophenyl) thiophene-2-yl] methyl}-4-methyl phenyl)-6-(hydroxyl methyl) oxane-3, 4, 5-triol (Figure-1b). It is used as an adjunct to diet and exercise to improve glycemic control in adults with T2DM in numerous countries worldwide. The recommended dose of Canagliflozin is 100 or 300 mg once daily (QD) [22-25].

Various ultraviolet spectroscopic and high performance liquid chromatographic assay methods were reported for the estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin individually and in combination with other drugs [31-59]. This draft is the simple and affordable validated method for the quantitation of Metformin and Canagliflozin the generic pharmaceutical industries.

This communication represents the validation for a simple, precise, accurate, sensitive and reproducible quantitative estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Figure 1.1: Chemical structure of Metformin.

Figure 1.2: Chemical structure of Canagliflozin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Apparatus.

Metformin and Canagliflozin were purchased from Mesochem Technology, Inc., Beijing, China. Methanol and Water were used of HPLC grade and purchased from Fisher Scientific, India. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Company, India. A double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer, model 1700, Shimadzu, Japan, with software UV Probe 2.10 and 1 cm quartz cell, was used for the analysis.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solutions.

Standard stock solution (100 µg/mL) of Metformin and Canagliflozin were prepared separately by dissolving accurately weighed 10mg of individual drug in 100 mL volumetric flask and diluting up to the mark with methanol.

Preparation of Working Standard Stock Solutions.

1ml from Metformin and 1 ml from Canagliflozin stock solutions were taken into a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up to mark with Methanol. (Metformin and Canagliflozin-10 µg/ml each respectively)

Preparation of Sample solution

Sample stock solution: Standard laboratory mixture equivalent to 10 mg of Metformin and Canagliflozin was diluted up to 100 ml with methanol. (Metformin and Canagliflozin-100 µg/ml each). This solution was filtered through whatman filter paper-1. Working sample preparation: 1 ml of above stock solution was diluted to 10 ml with methanol. (Metformin and Canagliflozin-10µg/ml each)

Determination of Iso-absorptive Point and Wavelength of Maximum Absorbance (λ_{\max}).

Solutions of 10µg/mL of Metformin and Canagliflozin were scanned in the range of 200 nm to 400 nm against methanol as blank. The method involved Q-absorption ratio analysis using two wavelengths obtained by the overlay spectrum of the Metformin and Canagliflozin; with one being the maximum absorbance wavelength of Canagliflozin (220 nm, λ_2) and the other being the iso-absorptive point of both drugs (250 nm, λ_1).

Preparation of Sample Solutions from Standard Stock Solution.

The sample solutions of various concentrations were prepared from the standard stock solution by diluting aliquots of working stock solutions appropriately.

Calibration Curve (Linearity).

The linearity response was determined by analyzing six independent levels of calibration curve in the range of 5-17.5 µg/mL for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively (n=3). Accurately measured stock solutions of Metformin and Canagliflozin (5.0, 7.5, 10.0, 12.5, 15.0 and 17.5 mL) were transferred to two separate series of 100 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with methanol. The absorbance of both solutions was taken at their respective λ_{\max} and at iso-absorptive point. The calibration curves were constructed by plotting concentration against absorbance where each data point was an average of three determinations.

2.8. *Estimation of Standard Laboratory Mixture using proposed method.* The absorptivity coefficient of both the drugs was determined. The individual concentration of Metformin and Canagliflozin was determined using the following equations:

$$C_{\text{Metformin}} = (Q_M - Q_Y) \times A_1 / (Q_X - Q_Y) \times a_{X1}$$

$$C_{\text{Canagliflozin}} = (Q_M - Q_X) \times A_1 / (Q_Y - Q_X) \times a_{Y1}$$

where, $Q_M = A_2/A_1$, $Q_X = a_{X2}/a_{X1}$, and $Q_Y = a_{Y2}/a_{Y1}$; A_1 and A_2 are the absorbance of the mixture at 250 nm and 240 nm respectively; a_{X1} and a_{Y1} are absorptivities at 250 nm (λ_1); a_{X2} and a_{Y2} are absorptivities at 220 nm (λ_2).

Method Validation**Linearity and Range**

Linearity, consisting of the basic elements input → converter → output, is the assumption that there is a straight line relationship between the input (x) and output (y) variables that can be written mathematically by the expression $y = f(x)$, if the straight line crosses through the origin or by the expression $y = f(x) + \delta$, if the straight line does not cross through the origin. The linear range corresponds to the valid interval of functional dependence of the signal on concentration or mass that assumes homoscedasticity of the measurements over the linear range. The linear response of Metformin and Canagliflozin was determined by analyzing six independent levels of the calibration curve in the range of 5–17.5 µg/mL.

Precision.

ICH guidelines define the term precision as the closeness of agreement between quantity values obtained by replicate measurements of a quantity under specified conditions^[11]. Assessing the precision implies expressing numerically the random error or the degree of dispersion of a set of individual measurements by means of the standard deviation, the variance, or the coefficient of variation.

Repeatability.

It is the concordance of a series of measurements of the same quantity when the experiments are conducted under same conditions (analyst, apparatus, instrument, and day) in a rapid succession. Standard solution of Metformin and Canagliflozin (10 µg/mL each) was prepared and analyzed six times as per the proposed method.

Intermediate Precision.

It is the concordance of a series of measurements of the same quantity when the experiments are conducted within the same laboratory under different conditions (analyst, apparatus, instrument, and day). Standard solution of Metformin and Canagliflozin (10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ each) was prepared and analyzed as per the proposed method.

Accuracy (% Recovery).

The accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value that is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found. The recovery experiments were carried out in triplicate by spiking previously analyzed samples with three different concentrations of standards.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ).

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in the sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in the sample that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The LOD and LOQ of the proposed method were determined by using calibration curve:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times [\text{Standard deviation of the response (Y-intercept of calibration curve)} / \text{Slope of the calibration curve}]$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times [\text{Standard deviation of the response (Y-intercept of calibration curve)} / \text{Slope of the calibration curve}]$$

Sandell's Sensitivity.

Sandell's sensitivity, the concentration of the analyte (in $\mu\text{g/mL}$ or $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$) that will give an absorbance of 0.001 in a cell of path length 1cm, was calculated. It gives valuable information regarding sensitivity of the method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The solutions of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of both Metformin and Canagliflozin were analyzed and the λ_{max} was found to be 220 nm and 240 nm respectively. Two iso-absorptive points: 230 nm and 250 nm were obtained by overlaying the spectra (Figure 3) and the iso-absorptive point 250 nm was selected for further analysis.

The calibration curve of Metformin and Canagliflozin individually and the mixture of both drugs at 220 nm (λ_1) and 250 nm (λ_2) were plotted (Figures 4, 5, and 6). The relationship between the absorbance and the concentration of Metformin and Canagliflozin was linear in the range of 5–17.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at both wavelengths 220nm and 250nm. The representative linear equations were calculated by the least squares method and the correlation coefficients were linear (Table 1). Evaluation of repeatability and intermediate precision was done and coefficients of variation (CV) or percent relative standard deviation (%RSD) values were <2%, indicating good precision (Table 2). Accuracy of the proposed method was calculated by percent recovery in standard addition method. Accuracy ranged between 99.65 and 101.91% for Metformin and 101.26 and 100.12% for Canagliflozin (Table 3). The limit of detection (LOD) of Metformin and Canagliflozin at iso-absorptive point (250 nm) was 0.106 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.078 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; at 220 nm, LOD was 0.186 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.211 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. The limit of quantification (LOQ) of Metformin and Canagliflozin at iso-absorptive point (250 nm) was 0.321 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.238 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; at 220 nm, LOQ was 0.563 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 0.639 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Metformin and Canagliflozin, respectively. Sandell's sensitivity was 0.0347 and 0.0348 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ at 250 nm and 0.022 and 0.035 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$ at 220 nm for Metformin and Canagliflozin, respectively. Various validation parameters are summarized in Table 4.

CONCLUSION

The UV spectrophotometric Q -absorption ratio method was developed and validated for the simultaneous analysis of Metformin and Canagliflozin. The results together established that the method is simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, rapid, and sensitive. The method can be applied successfully and economically for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin in bulk and in the synthetic laboratory mixture and also for the quantitation of generic equivalents in pharmaceutical industries.

Figure 3: UV scan of Metformin and Canagliflozin showing iso-absorptive points.

Figure 4: Calibration curve of Metformin and Canagliflozin at 250 nm, λ_1 .

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Metformin and Canagliflozin at 220 nm, λ_2 .

Table 1: Calibration points of standard curve with Absorbance and concentration of the solution.

Concentration of the solution ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance at 220 nm		Absorbance at 250 nm	
	Metformin	Canagliflozin	Metformin	Canagliflozin
5	0.149	0.192	0.095	0.19
7.5	0.277	0.375	0.242	0.278
10	0.525	0.515	0.422	0.358
12.5	0.711	0.686	0.655	0.525
15	0.985	0.811	0.882	0.655
17.5	1.257	1.205	1.185	0.789

Table 2: Precision.

Precision	Concentration of the solution ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	At 220 nm			At 250 nm			% Estimation of Canagliflozin (n = 6)	%RSD
		% Estimation of Metformin (n=6)	%RS D	% Estimation of Canagliflozin (n=6)	%RS D	% Estimation of Metformin (n=6)	%RS D		
Repeatability	10	0.514 \pm 0.003	0.502	0.356 \pm 0.002	0.674	0.526 \pm 0.002	0.288	0.424 \pm 0.002	0.504
Intra-day Precision	5	0.193 \pm 0.003	1.371	0.146 \pm 0.002	1.014	0.192 \pm 0.002	1.041	0.095 \pm 0.001	1.053
	10	0.515 \pm 0.001	0.224	0.525 \pm 0.002	0.397	0.356 \pm 0.002	0.429	0.424 \pm 0.002	0.594
	17.5	1.205 \pm 0.004	0.332	1.254 \pm 0.004	0.319	0.789 \pm 0.001	0.194	1.183 \pm 0.003	0.258
Inter-day Precision	5	0.192 \pm 0.003	1.826	0.147 \pm 0.001	1.041	0.191 \pm 0.003	1.597	0.095 \pm 0.001	1.053
	10	0.514 \pm 0.003	0.583	0.525 \pm 0.002	0.397	0.355 \pm 0.003	0.988	0.424 \pm 0.002	0.594
	17.5	1.201 \pm 0.007	0.584	1.254 \pm 0.004	0.319	0.784 \pm 0.004	0.575	1.183 \pm 0.003	0.258

Table 3: Results of recovery studies of Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Table 3.1: Results of recovery studies of Metformin.

Conc. Level (%)	Sample amount ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	% Mean Recovery \pm S.D
80 %	5	4	4.071	101.773	99.633 \pm 1.909
	5	4	3.961	99.022	
	5	4	3.924	98.105	
100 %	5	5	5.012	100.244	101.141 \pm 0.859
	5	5	5.098	101.956	
	5	5	5.061	101.222	
	5	6	5.929	98.818	
120 %	5	6	6.002	100.041	99.158 \pm 0.771
	5	6	5.917	98.615	

Table 3.2: Results of recovery studies of Canagliflozin.

Conc. Level (%)	Sample amount ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	% Mean Recovery \pm S.D
80 %	5	4	4.059	101.478	99.910 \pm 1.691
	5	4	3.925	98.118	
	5	4	4.005	100.134	
100 %	5	5	4.973	99.462	99.821 \pm 1.643
	5	5	5.081	101.613	
	5	5	4.919	98.387	
120 %	5	6	6.102	101.703	100.508 \pm 1.369
	5	6	5.941	99.014	
	5	6	6.048	100.806	

Table 4: Summary of regression characteristics and validation parameters.

Parameters	Metformin		Canagliflozin	
	220 nm	250 nm	220 nm	250 nm
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5 – 17.5	5 – 17.5	5 – 17.5	5 – 17.5
Absorptivity	0.05	0.035	0.05	0.04
Regression equation ($y = mx + c$)	$y=0.0797x - 0.2418$	$y=0.0491x - 0.0861$	$y = 0.0897x - 0.3586$	$y = 0.0869x - 0.3974$
Slope (m)	0.0797	0.0861	0.3586	0.0869
Intercept (c)	0.2418	0.0491	0.0897	0.3974
Regression coefficient (r^2)	0.98223	0.98714	0.98896	0.98627
Standard deviation of slope (SD)	0.017	0.031	0.043	0.043
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.747	1.567	1.581	1.581
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2.265	4.748	4.791	4.791
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2$)	0.0356	0.0347	0.0229	0.0348

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